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Drones See Signs

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Drones See Signs project, delivered in M4. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the **FAIR Data** section.

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TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package
ADR	Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road

ROS	Robot Operating System
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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, I followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Chung-Hsuan Ryan Lee (e52112880@student.tuwien.ac.at) will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Scripts	Source code	Python, Bash	100 - 1000 MB	no
P2	Docker images	Archived data	TAR	50 - 100 GB	no

Description for "Scripts":

These are Python and Bash scripts used to launch ROS2 nodes, it will allow the users to control the drone in offboard control mode, publish camera data, and run object detection inference pipelines. The files will be stored in .py .sh format with comments to explain the codes to increase reusability.

Description for "Docker images":

These are containerized environments that contain all dependencies required to make the project work "out of the box", ensuring reproducibility for potential users. This includes for example, YOLO, ROS2, CUDA libraries, Python packages etc.

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	ADR Signs	https://universe.roboflow.com/derya-logsd/adr-levha	CC BY 4.0	no

Description for "ADR Signs":

This is an existing ADR (hazard) sign dataset from the Roboflow Universe that I plan to re-use. This dataset includes images of ADR signs in the form of JPEG/PNG, bounding box labels and annotations in YOLO-format .txt, and metadata JSON/CSV describing the dataset properties.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data will be generated and re-used through a combination of existing ADR sign dataset and newly recorded drone sensor data. Firstly, R1 will be augmented and preprocessed using Roboflow to increase the tolerance. I will then split R1 by a 70/20/10 ratio to be re-used to train, validate, and test YOLO11 object detection models. After training, the best weight from the model is then extracted into the containerized environment to ensure reusability. ROS2 will be used to run nodes for controlling the drone and publishing camera data. Additional data, such as ROS topics like odometry, IMU, depth information, will be generated during drone test flights and stored as ROS2 bag files. Docker will then be used to containerize the full environment to ensure reproducibility.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community, anyone who is interested in the topics of drone research, autonomous drone flight and robot vision.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

I will make the data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata, ensuring long-term findability and citation. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

Each version of the dataset (e.g., model weights, ROS2 bag samples) will be clearly versioned so users can reference or reproduce specific states of the project.

A README file with an explanation of all terms used and codes to run at project level will be included. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse the data.

Additionally, I will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords (e.g., ADR signs, YOLO detection, ROS2, drone mapping, autonomous drone flight, computer vision) when publishing data. In this case, I will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, I will use controlled vocabularies for the data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

I will make the data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, I will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2026-02-03	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	MIT
P2	Open	2026-02-03	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it.

<https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: They need to have a PC or laptop to run the code and docker containers.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

I will make the data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within the field. As far as possible, I will use controlled vocabularies for the data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. I will provide good documentation for all the datasets, where project-specific terms (e.g., ADR sign class names or coordinate frame descriptions such as ENU/NED), will be fully explained in accompanying README files and matched to commonly used terminology in robotics and computer vision. All datasets will also include links or references to related external datasets and relevant software documentation (e.g., PX4 documentation), allowing users to combine the data with other resources to enhance interoperability.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

As mentioned in section 2.1, I will make the data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive README files to all published datasets, describing the methodology, data

structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, and any preprocessing steps. Code will be documented at file level, and configuration files (e.g., RViz setups, ROS2 launch files) will be included to allow replication of the flight experiments. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

Data quality will be ensured through standard procedures such as camera and sensor calibration, repeated measurements and recordings during test flights, consistent data capture process with the scripts, and internal peer review of scripts and results. Additional research outputs (Docker images, scripts, and trained model weights) will be included in the DMP considerations for long-term access and reproducibility.

3. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with [the work package leaders] being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

4. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

4.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Chung-Hsuan Ryan Lee (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P1 (Scripts) will be stored on TUGitLab: TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute's administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

P2 (Docker images) will be stored on TUcloud: TUcloud is a sync&share service provided by Campus IT for TU Wien members. It runs on Campus IT servers and offers features known from public cloud systems, such as Dropbox, for example, the exchange of data with authorised persons. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days.

4.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

I pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	writing
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	writing
R1	writing	reading only	reading only

4.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years

5. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

5.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

5.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Potential user have all rights to access all datasets.

5.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.